

1 **The differential development of microsporidia infecting worker honey bee (*Apis***
2 ***mellifera*) at increasing incubation temperature**

3 Mariano Higes¹, Pilar García-Palencia², Cristina Botías¹, Aránzazu Meana³, Raquel Martín-
4 Hernández¹

5 ¹Regional Apicultural Center, Dirección General de la Producción Agropecuaria,
6 Consejería de Agricultura, Junta de Comunidades de Castilla-La Mancha, Marchamalo,
7 Guadalajara, Spain.

8 ²Department of Veterinary Medicine and Surgery, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine,
9 Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain.

10 ³Department of Animal Health, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Universidad Complutense
11 de Madrid, Spain.

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15 **Abstract**

16 In the last century, nosemosis caused by *Nosema apis* is traditionally considered as a low-
17 prevalence disease of *Apis mellifera*, even though it occurs worldwide. Colonies affected
18 by *N. apis* display low levels of infection during summer, a small peak in autumn and
19 usually a slow rise during winter. However, nosemosis due to *Nosema ceranae* is
20 considered as an emergent illness that is posing a major threat to the health of individual
21 honey bees and whole bee colonies. The symptoms of infection by these two pathogens
22 are very different, as are the virulence, spread and pathogenicity. We have carried out
23 experiments in artificially infected worker honey bees maintained in the laboratory at two
24 different temperatures. Both microsporidia developed as expected for up to 4 days after
25 infection at 33.0°C, but when maintained for 5 or 7 days at 37.2°C, only *N. ceranae*
26 completed its life cycle in infected honey bees, while the development of *N. apis* was
27 inhibited. This and other published data suggest that *N. ceranae* is eurythermal whereas
28 *N. apis* is stenothermal. The higher temperature tolerance recorded may be related to the
29 higher prevalence of *N. ceranae* reported worldwide.

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39 Introduction

40 *Nosema apis* causes one of the most important diseases of honey bees, although it is
41 generally overlooked by beekeepers (Burnside and Revell, 1948; Hornitzky, 2005).
42 Outbreaks of nosemosis were believed to be the result of poor beekeeping practices or
43 other problems, such as poor wintering conditions, poor dietary pollen quality or other
44 pathologies or toxins. Infection by *N. apis* gradually declines during the warm summer
45 months until it disappears, although it generally resurges later in autumn and spring (Doull
46 and Eckert, 1962). These epidemiological cycles may reflect the favourable environmental
47 temperatures in these seasons (Burnside and Revell, 1948; Dyes and Wilson, 1978) and
48 the decrease in viable spores inside the hive (Bailey, 1955). Indeed, in honey bees, *N. apis*
49 spores are rarely found in summer or winter, and they may only be detected in heavily
50 infected honey bee colonies (OIE, 2008).

51 In contrast, emergent nosemosis caused by *Nosema ceranae*, now named nosemosis
52 type C (COLOSS Workshop, 2009; Higes et al., 2010), is considered a major threat to
53 honey bee colonies (Higes et al., 2008a; Chen et al., 2009; Cornman et al., 2009) and
54 infection produces symptoms very different from *N. apis* (Higes et al., 2008a; 2009; 2010;
55 COLOSS Workshop, 2009). In recent years, natural infection by this microsporidian has
56 been associated with a gradual loss of worker and forager bees, copious colony death in
57 the autumn or winter, and poor honey production (Higes et al., 2006; 2008a; 2009; Martín-
58 Hernández et al., 2007; Botías et al., 2009; Korpela, 2009). In addition, infection by *N.*
59 *ceranae* suppresses the honey bee's immune response and induces senescence (Antúnez
60 et al., 2009), and it now seems to be capable of infecting other hymenoptera (Plischuk et
61 al., 2009), properties not yet associated with *N. apis*.

62 Temperature clearly affects the endogenous life cycle of both microsporidia distinctly
63 (Martín-Hernández et al., 2009) and although the biotic potential was similar for both *N.*
64 *apis* and *N. ceranae* at 33.0°C, this index was higher at 25.0°C and 37.0°C for *N. ceranae*.
65 The better capacity of *N. ceranae* to adapt to and complete its endogenous cycle at
66 different temperatures reflects the epidemiological differences between these
67 microsporidia in field conditions.

68 The aim of this study was to examine the higher tolerance of *N. ceranae* to high
69 temperatures when compared with *N. apis*. Accordingly, experimentally infected worker
70 honey bees were maintained at 33.0°C to enhance their endogenous life cycle (as
71 described Martín-Hernández et al., 2009) and then the temperature was shifted to 37.2°C,
72 which has been reported to inhibit *N. apis* development (Burnside and Revell, 1948).

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74 Results and discussion

75 At 33.0°C, both microsporidia developed as expected from day 4 pi (post infection:
76 Martín-Hernández et al., 2009), as evident from the intracellular stages of each
77 microsporidium in the ventricular epithelial cells of *N. apis*- and *N. ceranae*-infected
78 worker honey bees (Fig. 1A and B). In contrast, no *Nosema* infection was evident in any of
79 the control uninfected bees throughout the study [transmission electron microscopy
80 (TEM) studies and mean spore count]. When the infected worker honey bees were shifted
81 to 37.2°C for 5 days, no immature stages of the microsporidium were observed in the
82 ventricular cells of bees infected with *N. apis*. Indeed, the mature spores of this species

83 displayed clear signs of degeneration, such as the absence of polar filament coils, a
84 nucleus and other such structures (Fig. 2A). In contrast, not only were some immature
85 stages found inside the ventricular epithelial cells in the worker honey bees infected by *N.*
86 *ceranae* but also, infective mature spores with structures characteristic of this
87 microsporidium were evident, indicating that *N. ceranae* were still multiplying (Fig. 2B).

88 A frame with capped brood of *Apis mellifera* worker bees was taken from a *Nosema*-free
89 colony and maintained in an incubator at 35°C until the bees were born (Higes et al.,
90 2007; Martín-Hernández et al., 2009). Newly emerged worker bees were carefully
91 removed from the frame, confined to cages and kept in a different incubator for 5 days at
92 33°C. On the day of infection, 10 bees from each cage were taken to confirm the absence
93 of *Nosema* spp. by PCR, and they were infected as described in Higes and colleagues
94 (2007). Briefly, 5-day-old bees were starved for 2 h and subsequently, each bee was fed
95 with 2 µl of water containing 100 000 viable *Nosema ceranae* or *Nosema apis* spores
96 while uninfected control bees were fed with 2 µl of water alone. Infections were carried out
97 with purified *N. apis* and *N. ceranae* spores (confirmed by PCR; Martín-Hernández et al.,
98 2007) with a minimum viability of 99% (as tested with 0.4% trypan blue: Higes et al.,
99 2008b; Martín-Hernández et al., 2009). The experiment involved the use of two groups of
100 15 *N. apis*-infected honey bees, two groups of 15 *N. ceranae*-infected honey bees, and
101 two groups of 15 uninfected honey bees (control). Three different incubators (33°C) were
102 used for the *N. apis*- and *N. ceranae*-infected or the controls bees (Martín-Hernández et
103 al., 2009). Four days post infection (pi), two living honey bees were removed from each of
104 the replicate groups (n = 12 bees) and their ventriculi, with the Malpighian tubes attached,
105 were processed as described previously (Higes et al., 2007; 2008a; 2009) for transmission
106 electron microscopy (TEM) studies to confirm the successful infection. At that time (4 day
107 pi), the temperature was increased in the three incubators to 37.2°C and the living bees
108 were maintained at this temperature for up to 11 days pi in new cages (to avoid them
109 contacting the spores that were contaminating them). Subsequently, two honey bees from
110 each replicate group were processed for TEM on days 9 and 11 pi as indicated previously.
111 The midguts from the bees remaining at 11 pi (n = 9 for each replicate) were individually
112 placed in a sterile microtube in 200 µl of ddH₂O (PCR grade). After grinding thoroughly
113 (Eppendorf), the spore count for each bee was calculated with a haemocytometer and in
114 addition, PCR was used to confirm the *Nosema* species present.

115 When these bees were maintained for 2 more days at 37.2°C (day 11 pi), mature and
116 immature stages of the microsporidia were only visible inside the ventricular epithelial
117 cells of bees infected by *N. ceranae*. In bees infected by *N. apis* there was no evidence of
118 this microsporidia at any stages of its life cycle in the ventricular epithelial cells.

119 On day 12 pi, all honey bees infected by *N. ceranae* were dead (n = 9 for each replicate)
120 with a mean mature spore count per bee of $421 (\pm 21.1) \times 10^3$ (mean \pm standard deviation).
121 In contrast, bees in the control group or those infected with *N. apis* remained alive (n =
122 9 for each group) and no spores were detected.

123 We have shown that *N. ceranae* is capable of completing its full biological life cycle at
124 temperatures as high as 37.2°C, temperatures that appear to inhibit the development of *N.*
125 *apis* in TEM studies and through the mean spore count. These results agree with previous
126 data demonstrating that honey bees infected by *N. apis* recover when they are kept at
127 37.0–37.2°C for 1–14 days (Karmo and Morgenthaler, 1939; Lotmar, 1944; Burnside and
128 Revell, 1948) and that the viability of *N. apis* spores decreases steadily over time at

129 temperatures close to 40°C (Malone et al., 2001). In the honey bees infected with *N.*
130 *apis*, mature spores within the epithelial ventricular cells display clear signs of
131 degeneration when they were maintained for 5 days at 37.2°C. Indeed, at this temperature
132 all the parasitic forms of this microsporidium had disappeared 2 days later and no mature
133 spores were detected in the bees. In contrast, the full biological life cycle was still
134 completed in the bees infected with *N. ceranae*, and mature and immature stages of this
135 microsporidium could be observed inside the epithelial ventricular cells at this
136 temperature, finally leading to the death of the infected workers. Indeed, in terms of
137 survival, these results are in agreement with previous studies suggesting that *N. ceranae* is
138 more virulent than *N. apis* in caged worker honey bees (Higes et al., 2007; Paxton et
139 al., 2007).

140 In addition, these results confirmed earlier data demonstrating that *N. ceranae* is better
141 adapted to different temperatures (Martín-Hernández et al., 2009), and that it can
142 complete its endogenous cycle with a higher biotic index from 25.0°C to 37.0°C,
143 supporting the epidemiological differences between these microsporidia in field
144 conditions. Indeed, while mature and immature stages of *N. ceranae* can be detected in
145 infected honey bees in all four seasons (Martín-Hernández et al., 2007; Higes et al.,
146 2008a), *N. apis* infection is more prevalent in the milder spring or autumn seasons (Bailey,
147 1955; Doull and Eckert, 1962; Dyes and Wilson, 1978; OIE, 2008) when temperatures are
148 less extreme than in winter or summer.

149 The presence of *N. ceranae* in colder, and especially in hotter months, may be due to its
150 eurythermality (Martín-Hernández et al., 2009), a characteristic that could contribute to
151 the higher worldwide prevalence of *N. ceranae*, and to its importance in causing an
152 emerging worldwide disease named type C nosemosis (COLOSS Workshop, 2009; Higes
153 et al., 2010). Global climate change produces ecological perturbations that cause
154 geographical and phenological shifts, as well as altering the dynamics of parasite
155 transmission. Indeed, on this basis climate change appears to enhance host-switching
156 (Brooks and Hoberg, 2007) and it may also affect the conditions of certain microhabitats,
157 facilitating the colonization of novel areas by parasites.

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Figure 1

253 A frame with capped brood of *Apis mellifera* worker bees was taken from a *Nosema*-
254 free colony and maintained in an incubator at 35°C until the bees were born (Higes *et*
255 *al.*, 2007; Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2009). Newly emerged worker bees were carefully
256 removed from the frame, confined to cages and kept in a different incubator for 5 days
257 at 33°C. On the day of infection, 10 bees from each cage were taken to confirm the
258 absence of *Nosema* spp. by PCR, and they were infected as described in Higes and
259 colleagues (2007). Briefly, 5-day-old bees were starved for 2 h and subsequently, each
260 bee was fed with 2 µl of water containing 100 000 viable *Nosema ceranae* or *Nosema*
261 *apis* spores while uninfected control bees were fed with 2 µl of water alone.
262 Infections were carried out with purified *N. apis* and *N. ceranae* spores (confirmed by
263 PCR; Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2007) with a minimum viability of 99% (as tested with
264 0.4% trypan blue: Higes *et al.*, 2008b; Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2009). The
265 experiment involved the use of two groups of 15 *N. apis*-infected honey bees, two
266 groups of 15 *N. ceranae*-infected honey bees, and two groups of 15 uninfected honey
267 bees (control). Three different incubators (33°C) were used for the *N. apis*- and *N.*
268 *ceranae*-infected or the controls bees (Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2009). Four days post
269 infection (pi), two living honey bees were removed from each of the replicate groups (*n*
270 = 12 bees) and their ventriculi, with the Malpighian tubes attached, were processed as
271 described previously (Higes *et al.*, 2007; 2008a; 2009) for transmission electron
272 microscopy (TEM) studies to confirm the successful infection. At that time (4 day pi),
273 the temperature was increased in the three incubators to 37.2°C and the living bees
274 were maintained at this temperature for up to 11 days pi in new cages (to avoid them
275 contacting the spores that were contaminating them). Subsequently, two honey bees
276 from each replicate group were processed for TEM on days 9 and 11 pi as indicated
277 previously. The midguts from the bees remaining at 11 pi (*n* = 9 for each replicate) were
278 individually placed in a sterile microtube in 200 µl of ddH₂O (PCR grade). After
279 grinding thoroughly (Eppendorf), the spore count for each bee was calculated with a
280 haemocytometer and in addition, PCR was used to confirm the *Nosema* species
281 present.

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289 A. Ventricular epithelial cell infected by *N. apis* from 4 days pi at 33°C filled with
 290 different parasitic stages: meronts (M), mature spores (MS), empty spore (ES),
 291 Vacuoles (V), Microvilli (mv). Scale bar = 5 µm.

292 B. Ventricular epithelial cell infected by *N. ceranae* from 4 days pi at 33°C. Different
 293 parasitic stages: meronts (M), mature spores (MS). Note the apically displaced
 294 nucleus (N). Scale bar = 5 µm.

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298 **Figure 2**

299 A. Ventricular epithelial cell infected by *Nosema apis* after 5 days at 37.2°C. Degenerated
 300 mature spores and numerous vacuoles in the cytoplasm. Scale bar = 2 µm.

301 B. Ventricular epithelial cell infected by *Nosema ceranae* after 5 days at 37.2°C. Different
 302 parasitic stages: meronts (M), mature spores (MS). Moderate cell degeneration. Scale bar
 303 = 5 µm.

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